

FINANCIAL LITERACY OF THE SELECTED GOVERNMENT EMPLOYEES IN DAET, CAMARINES NORTE: BASIS FOR IEC MATERIALS DEVELOPMENT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13733697>

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to assess the financial literacy of government personnel in Daet, Camarines Norte, for IEC material development. Descriptive-correlational methods were used to analyze data from 358 respondents, collected through online surveys and interviews. Financial literacy was measured across spending, saving, investing, and availing insurance. The study found that most respondents were female, aged 26-33, married, college graduates, and had a monthly income of PHP 24,601-39,400. While respondents generally demonstrated adequate financial literacy, key challenges included budget constraints and limited financial training. The study recommends that government agencies provide financial literacy training, develop and implement IEC materials, and promote financial tracking tools to enhance employee financial well-being.

Keywords: *Financial literacy, personal finance, savings, spending, investing, availing insurance, budgeting, investment, decision making.*

INTRODUCTION

Recognizing how to manage money well is widely seen as a key part of handling finances and fostering economic growth. This includes the skills and knowledge needed to make informed decisions about money and manage financial matters effectively. Those

who grasp finances well can better handle complicated accounting tasks, plan for the future, and achieve their financial goals (Lusardi and Mitchell, 2014).

Different people have different understandings of financial literacy. For some, it is a broad concept involving understanding the economy and how financial factors affect family decisions. Others focus on basic money management skills such as saving, budgeting, investing, and insurance. Financial literacy ultimately means understanding and making wise decisions about one's financial situation and resources (Schagen and Lines, 1996).

In order to possess a strong understanding of finances, individuals must adopt responsible financial habits that enable them to recognize different financial products and services with confidence. This behavioral change can be initiated by introducing financial education early on. Since childhood habits often persist into adulthood, children must learn financial concepts as soon as possible (Dwiastanti, 2015).

Unlike in other industrialized countries, financial literacy has not yet become a priority in India. Because a lack of fundamental financial understanding leads to bad investments and financial decisions, most individuals invest in short-term plans and physical assets to meet their own goals, which generate lower returns and do not contribute to the country's economic progress (Pathak and Nathani, 2020).

According to Bureau of the Treasury (2022), 80 percent of the Filipino population is unprepared financially for retirement, 97 percent of the population has no assets, and 75 percent of the population is financially illiterate. Poor financial judgments and investment mistakes will be made in the absence of financial knowledge and competence, potentially leading to poor economic effects.

In response to this issue, according to Dela Cruz (2022) the Civil Service Commission, the Bangko Sentral ng Pilipinas, and the BDO Foundation launched the financial education program for civil servants to educate government personnel about financial matters. This curriculum aims to instruct public employees in the areas of financial preparation, savings strategies, spending techniques, handling debts, ways to invest, combating financial deception, and safeguarding consumer rights. The CSC Chairperson has said that the organization would accomplish its objective of improving the welfare of government employees by promoting financial literacy. As part of this process, they will provide them with the knowledge and tools they need to manage their money wisely. With the help of the financial awareness initiatives, the government workers will be better equipped to save more money, borrow wisely, invest wisely, prepare for retirement, and stay safe in this age of online banking and electronic payment methods. The Department of Education has formulated a Personal Finance Strategy in accordance with DepEd Order No. 022, section 2021. This aligns with Republic Act No. 10922, commonly referred to as the 2016 Economic and Financial Literacy Act, and Republic Act No. 10670, also known as the 2015 Youth Entrepreneurship Act. The objective of the DepEd Policy is to augment the integration of Financial Education while

elevating the financial comprehension and capacity to make choices of staff, professors, and learners, hence fostering financial inclusion and health.

Having a solid understanding of finances is essential for individuals to make informed choices, take advantage of economic prospects, and attain financial well-being. Literate citizens can help alleviate poverty and promote inclusive growth by promoting quality education that equips more people with the skills they need to be productive members of society and to understand and manage their own money. This aligns with the goals of the Sustainable Development Goals and the Ambisyon Natin 2040: Matatag, Maginhawa, at Panatag na Buhay (NEDA, n.d.).

Government personnel play a crucial role in ensuring the smooth operation of government affairs. Typically, they receive stable salaries, benefits, and access to retirement plans as part of their employment package. However, the level of financial literacy among government employees greatly influences their financial well-being, future preparedness, and ability to make informed financial decisions. To enhance the financial competence and overall financial outcomes of government workers, it is imperative to assess their current level of financial literacy thoroughly. This assessment serves as a foundation for implementing targeted strategies aimed at improving financial literacy within this important sector.

Public financial management is greatly impacted by the public sector. Examining government workers' knowledge of money matters, including spending, saving, investing, and insurance, is crucial. This analysis can greatly impact their personal financial well-being and the efficient use of public resources.

Evaluating government officials' financial literacy in spending, saving, investing, and insurance is critical for fostering responsible fiscal practices, effective resource allocation, and improved financial well-being. The public sector's financial health may be improved if lawmakers equip government employees with the information they need to make educated financial decisions. This can be achieved by identifying areas where financial literacy is lacking and implementing specific educational initiatives. As a result, it fosters improved governance of public finances, enhanced transparency, and superior public service delivery.

Research Questions

Generally, this study aimed to describe the financial literacy of the selected government employees in Daet, Camarines Norte as basis for Information, Education, and Communication (IEC) material development. Specifically, this study provides answers to the following questions:

1. How may the profile of the respondents be described along:
 - 1.1. sex;
 - 1.2. age;

- 1.3. marital status;
 - 1.4. highest educational attainment.
 - 1.5. monthly income; and
 - 1.6. length of service
 2. What is the level of financial literacy of the respondents along:
 - 2.1. spending;
 - 2.2. savings;
 - 2.3. investing; and
 - 2.4. availing insurance
 3. Is there a significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and their level of financial literacy?
 4. What are the problems affecting the financial literacy of the respondents?
 5. Based from the findings of the study, what IEC materials may be developed to improve the financial literacy of the respondents?
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METHODOLOGY

The descriptive-correlational research method was employed in this study. Research methods that aimed to characterize the features of the population or phenomena under study are known as descriptive research (Bhat, 2019). The researcher employed a descriptive research strategy to know how many government employees in Daet, Camarines Norte, fell into certain categories: sex, age, marital status, educational attainment, monthly income, and length of service. In addition, the study used a Likert scale to determine the extent to which selected federal government employees are financially literate in relation to spending, saving, investing, and insurance usage. It is a rating scale that uses a sequence of questions/statements to assess opinions, attitudes, or conduct (Pritha and Kassiani, 2023).

Additional methods that were utilized included correlational analysis. This research approach does not include doing experiments. Without the influence of a confounding variable, every researcher looks at two variables, finds a statistical connection among them, and then assesses it. The correlation coefficient measures the degree of the association between two variables (Fleetwood, 2021). As a result, this strategy is utilized to establish whether there is a substantial link between the profile and the various social media marketing methods employed.

Population, Sample Size, and Sampling Technique

According to the study's description of the respondents, the total population is 1,827 based on the number of workers of National Government Agencies (NGAs) reported by their respective organizations in 2023. The statistician calculated the sample size of the target group to be 358 using Slovin's formula and all agencies in Daet, Camarines Norte with less than 15 identified permanent workers.

Description of the Respondents

The respondents were the chosen national government employees from Daet, Camarines Norte. The selected National Government Agencies are the following: Bureau of Fire Protection (BFP); Bureau of Internal Revenue (BIR); Bureau of the Treasury (BTr); Cooperative Development Authority (CDA); Camarines Norte State College (CNSC); Commission on Elections (COMELEC); Civil Service Commission (CSC); Department of Agriculture (DA); Department of Agrarian Reform (DAR); Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR); Department of Education (DepEd); Department of Information and Communications (DICT); Department of Health (DOH); Department of Science and Technology (DOST); Department of Public Works and Highways (DPWH); Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD); Department of Trade and Industry (DTI); Registry of Deeds – Land Registration Authority (ROD-LRA); Land Transportation Office (LTO); National Bureau of Investigation (NBI); Philippine Coconut Authority (PCA); Philippine Information Agency (PIA); Philippine National Police (PNP); Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA); and Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA). They were described with their profile on sex, age, marital status, educational level, monthly salary, and duration of service. Respondents were only the permanent employees as of 2023 in this survey. Most of the respondent's years of service ranged from 1 – 5 and the longer the employees are in service the lesser the retention of the employees are.

Research Instrument

The major data gathering instrument for the study is a survey questionnaire created by the researcher. The google form was utilized to pave the way for the study's data. The research questionnaires are broken into three (3) components that alter depending on the information needed for the analysis. The first section contains information about the selected national government employees in Daet, Camarines such as their age, marital status, greatest educational attainment, monthly income, and term of employment. The second component is the respondents' level of agreement with the elements influencing investment decisions, which include savings, spending, investing, and insurance. The third and last section focuses on the issues impacting the financial literacy of employees of National Government Agencies (NGAs) in Daet, Camarines Norte.

Data Gathering Procedure

The survey questionnaire created by the researcher was reviewed by the researcher's mentor and members of the thesis advisory committee. It was based on the readings of literature related to the topic. It subjected to the necessary tests on the relevance and significance of the claims to guarantee that the data obtained is critical to the analysis's goals and objectives. The thesis advisory committee reviews and

scrutinizes the questionnaire created by the researcher. After that, dry run or pilot testing was performed to determine the usability and correctness of the questionnaire.

A dry run was conducted with twenty (20) respondents from Daet, Camarines Norte. This exercise demonstrated the consistency of the questionnaire's questions, components, and measurements, and it was used to identify potential questionnaire errors as well as to check the questionnaire's validity. The reliability test results indicated 0.967 using Cronbach's alpha, indicating that there is an internal consistency in the survey questionnaire. The researcher first sought the data from the designated National Government Agencies to determine their total population, and then the statistician computes the sample size for each agency.

The researcher then sent a request letter through the respective email addresses of the selected government agency in Daet, Camarines Norte, requesting permission to perform data collection. The letter includes the link and QR code for the respondents to access the survey questionnaire and answer through a Google form. However, most of the agencies did not acknowledge the request letter and for those who did, their employees do not prefer answering online. Due to that, the researcher proceeded to physically submit the letter to the respective offices of the agencies. Upon approval, the researcher begins with the data gathering with the respondents. The details were gathered, collated, and evaluated to give specific findings. The researcher assured that the information gathered would be used just for academic reasons and would be kept totally secret. The college's ethical research guidelines were conscientiously observed.

Statistical Treatment of Data

Using a variety of statistical techniques and methods, the data collected in this study is examined and understood. The quantitative data were mainly studied using descriptive and correlational statistical techniques. To use descriptive statistics, the variables must be specified, as well as the typical relationships that evolved between and within them. Correlational approaches are used to show when and how strongly two variables are related statistically. The percentage frequency distribution approach is used to determine the profile.

The weighted mean, on the other hand, was used to assess the level of financial literacy of NGA employees. The weighted mean is used to compute the responses of the respondents to determine the relative importance of the factors. A correlation statistic was employed to ascertain if there is a noteworthy connection between the respondent profile and their degree of financial literacy; Somer's Delta and Correlation coefficient were employed for this purpose. To quantify the degree of association between two categories, statisticians used the Contingency Coefficient as statistical tool. It is a non-parametric measure, which means it makes no assumptions about the data distribution. It is useful in research because it may be used to measure the strength of a link between two categorical variables and to test hypotheses regarding that relationship. It is a flexible and

powerful tool that may be utilized in a variety of applications. While Somers' Delta is useful in research because it can be used to measure the strength of a link between two ordinal variables and to test hypotheses regarding that relationship. It is a versatile and powerful tool that may be applied in a variety of settings (Agresti, 2013).

RESULTS

Table 1
Sex Profile of the Respondents

Sex	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	142	39.7
Female	216	60.3
Total	358	100.0

Table 2
Age Profile of the Respondents

Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)
18-25	8	2.2
26-33	102	28.5
34-41	80	22.3
42-49	87	24.3
50-57	52	14.5
58-65	29	8.1
Total	358	100.0

Table 3
Civil Status of the Respondents

Civil Status	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Single	111	31.0
Married	220	61.5
Seperated	5	1.4
Widowed	2	0.6
Total	358	100.0

Table 4
Profile of the Respondents in terms of Educational Attainment

Education	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Elementary Graduate	1	0.3
High School Level	3	0.8
High School Graduate	1	0.3
College Level	9	2.5
College Graduate	138	38.5

With units in Masters	121	33.8
Master's degree Holder	44	12.3
With units in Doctorate	17	4.7
Doctorate degree Holder	23	6.4
LLB	1	0.3
Total	358	100.0

Table 5
Profile of the Respondents in terms of Monthly Income

Amount	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Below ₱13,000	6	1.7
₱13,001 - ₱17,500	32	8.9
₱17,501 - ₱24,600	67	18.7
₱24,601 - ₱39,400	164	45.8
₱39,401 - ₱63,500	56	15.6
₱63,501 - ₱115,000	32	8.9
₱115,001 - ₱211,200	1	0.3
Total	358	100.0

Table 6
Profile of the Respondents in terms of Year in Service

Years in Service	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1-5	105	29.2
6-10	89	24.9
11-15	57	15.9
16-20	33	9.2
21-25	29	8.1
26-30	21	5.9
Above 30	3	0.8
Total	358	100.0

Table 7
Level of Financial Literacy of the Respondents on Investment Decision along Spending

Indicators	WM	Interpretation
1. I track all my expenses	3.64	A
2. I compare prices for major expenses	3.46	A
3. I use a spending plan or budget	3.76	A
4. I spend less than my income	3.56	A

5. I purchase only what I need	3.74	A
6. I purchased a financial product after gathering information about it	3.18	NAD
7. I follow some kind of rule in spending such as the 70-20-10. 70% - take home pay needs, 20% spending on wants and 10% on savings	3.62	A
8. I can distinguish my wants and needs when spending	3.77	A
9. I keep my debt to a minimum to ensure timely payment	3.91	A
10. I understand the importance of resisting the temptation to spend the money on shopping	3.82	A
Overall Weighted Mean	3.65	A

Legend:

4.21-5.00 - Strongly Agree (SA)

1.81-2.60 - Disagree (D)

3.41-4.20 - Agree (A)

1.00-1.80 - Strongly Disagree (SD)

2.61-3.40 - Neither Agree nor Disagree (NAD)

Table 8
Level of Financial Literacy of the Respondents on Investment Decision along Savings

Indicators	WM	Interpretation
1. I save out of each money I receive	3.79	A
2. I save at least 10 percent of my gross monthly income	3.96	A
3. I set long term financial goals and strive to achieve them	3.59	A
4. I increase my savings when I receive increase in salary	3.75	A
5. I keep track of all my expenses to cut some spending and save more	3.82	A
6. I am satisfied with my present rate of savings and investment accumulation	3.58	A

Overall Weighted Mean 3.62 A

Legend:

4.21-5.00 - Strongly Agree (SA) 1.81-2.60 - Disagree (D)
 3.41-4.20 - Agree (A) 1.00-1.80 - Strongly Disagree (SD)
 2.61-3.40 - Neither Agree nor Disagree (NAD)

Table 10
 Level of Financial Literacy of the Respondents on Investment Decision
 along Availing Insurance

Indicators	WM	Interpretation
1. I am well knowledgeable about the various terms that pertain to insurance	3.56	A
2. I am familiar with the procedures involved in insurance	3.51	A
3. I am familiar with the different forms of insurance: auto, home, business, life annuities and health	3.53	A
4. I consider the different benefits of the insurances	3.68	A
5. I conduct research prior to purchasing insurance	3.59	A
6. I am able to select the proper insurance for my needs	3.59	A
7. As a policyholder, I verify the insurance firm's I am considering if it's licensed or registered by the country's regulatory agency	3.69	A
8. I recognize that the insurance industry exists to protect me from potential risks, accidents, and uncertainties	3.72	A
9. I am aware that insurance companies may incur losses in the event of natural disasters, massive incidents, or extensive claims	3.69	A
10. I understand that insurance companies earn money by investing the premiums I pay	3.77	A
Overall Weighted Mean	3.63	A

Legend:

4.21-5.00 - Strongly Agree (SA)

1.81-2.60 - Disagree (D)

3.41-4.20 - Agree (A)

1.00-1.80 - Strongly Disagree (SD)

2.61-3.40 -Neither Agree nor Disagree (NAD)

Table 11

Test for Significant Relationship between the Profile of the Respondents and their Level of Financial Literacy on Investment Decision

Profile	Financial Literacy							
	Spending		Saving		Investing		Availing	
	Test Statistics	p-value	Test Statistics	p-value	Test Statistics	p-value	Test Statistics	p-value
Sex	.071	.770	-.178*	.020	.112	.342	.228*	.001
Age	.074	.153	.059	.242	.045	.374	-.001	.985
Civil Status	.166	.859	.183	.717	.148	.949	.196	.575
Educational Attainment	.077	.050	.097	.052	.059	.233	.036	.055
Monthly Income	.129*	.004	-.180*	.000	.199*	.010	.078	.089
Years in Service	.070	.178	.095	.063	.059	.238	.023	.634

*Significant @.05 level

Table 12

Problems Affecting the Financial Literacy on Investment Decision

Problems	Frequency	Rank
Limited financial training opportunities	156	3
Limited time	140	4
Heavy workload	170	2
Risk-averse culture	59	9
Lack of financial incentives	127	5
Limited access to independent financial advice	66	8
Lack of awareness of investment options	117	6
Complex insurance policies	69	7
Budget constraints and resource allocation	189	1
Technological advancements	38	10

Table 13

Proposed Action Plan to Institutionalize the IEC Materials Developed

Objective	Activity	Target Audience	Resources
Internal Training	Conduct training sessions on the I.E.C. material	Bureau of the Treasury personnel	I.E.C. materials, training materials, trainers
Resource Availability	Ensure I.E.C. material is readily accessible internally	Bureau intranet, training library, employee handbook	Digital copies of I.E.C. materials
Client Interaction	Integrate I.E.C. material into client interactions	Presentations, brochures, client service training	I.E.C. materials, adapted scripts
Website & Publications	Make I.E.C. material available online and in print	Bureau website, brochures, annual reports	I.E.C. materials, web developers
Social Media Engagement	Share financial literacy tips and infographics	Bureau social media platforms	I.E.C. materials, graphic designers
Seminars, Partnerships, & Collaborations	Webinars on financial topics. Distribute material and co-organize events	Stakeholders. Educational institutions, community organizations, financial institutions	I.E.C. materials, speakers, online platform. Proposals
Media Outreach	Collaborate with media outlets to promote I.E.C. material	Radio Stations	Press releases, media contacts
Focus Groups & Surveys	Gather feedback from internal and external users	Bureau personnel, workshop attendees, online surveys	Survey platform, facilitator
I.E.C. Material Updates	Review and adapt I.E.C. material based on feedback and trends	All stakeholders (internal and external)	I.E.C. material, subject matter experts

DISCUSSION

Profile of the Respondents

The profile of the respondents was determined, and they were classified based on respondents' age, sex, marital status, highest educational attainment, monthly income, and length of service. These data are presented in Tables 1 to 6.

Sex. **Table 1** for the sex profile of the respondents shows that out of the 358 government employees, female has the higher frequency of 216 and a percentage of 60.30 than male which only have a frequency of 142 with the percentage of 39.70.

The findings revealed that majority of government employees of national government agencies in Daet, Camarines Norte are females. One interpretation of this is that it suggests that female employees dominate the population of NGAs. This implies that there are many female populations in the province. It is parallel with Watkins (2020) which stated that women tend to exhibit higher levels of productivity due to the inherent necessity of balancing domestic, professional, and social responsibilities.

The lower proportion of males employed in NGAs can be attributed to various factors, including the higher likelihood of men working as self-employed individuals or in the private sector (Kuang-Ta, 2020). This finding is supported by Richard (2022), who suggests that government jobs tend to be more family-friendly, offering flexible work arrangements and better benefits such as paid leave and health insurance. These aspects may be particularly appealing to women who are balancing work and family responsibilities. Therefore, the combination of preferences for different types of employment and the attractiveness of government jobs to women may contribute to the lower proportion of males employed in NGAs.

Age. **Table 2** for the age profile of the respondents shows that out of the 358 respondents of National government agencies in Daet, Camarines Norte, the age bracket with the highest frequency amounting to 102 are ages 26-33 with a percentage of 28.5 while the age bracket with the lowest frequency amounting to 8 is age 18-25 with 2.20 percent. It shows that by ranking, the highest in rank is on age bracket 26 to 33 with 102 in frequency, second is 42 to 49 with 87 frequencies, third is 34 to 41 with 80 frequencies, fourth is 50 to 57 with 52 frequencies, fifth is 58 to 65 with 29 in frequencies, and lastly is the bracket under 18 to 25 with the least frequency of 8.

As for the age group of 26 to 33, which is the highest age brackets. People in this age range generally begin forming their own families and have children and may be searching for professions that give stability and security for themselves and their families. They are also building their professional growth to secure their family's future by being a government employee with security of tenure.

The data from the Philippine Statistics Authority (2022) supports the observation that a significant proportion of Filipinos aged 26 to 33, 34 to 49, and 50 and over have attained a college degree or higher academic qualification. Given that government occupations often require a college degree or higher level of education, it is understandable why individuals in these age groups are more frequently employed in NGAs. Furthermore, government jobs typically offer secure employment, which may be particularly appealing to individuals seeking stability in their careers. Therefore, the higher frequency of employment among these age groups in NGAs can be attributed to both the educational requirements of government positions and the desire for secure employment opportunities.

The lowest age range is from 18 to 25 because people in this age group are typically at the beginning of their careers and may have less work experience. Government jobs often require a certain amount of work experience, so younger workers may be less qualified for these positions. Also, at age 18 to 22 given the added two years for senior high school program, majority graduates at age 22 or higher. It means that there is a smaller chance of getting hired in government agencies with these age range. In support of this result, many government jobs in the Philippines require specialized education and training, which may not be completed until the employee is in their early to mid-20s. For example, teachers, nurses, and engineers typically need to complete college degrees before they can begin working in their respective fields (Executive Order No. 292 [BOOK V/Title I/Subtitle A/Chapter 5-Personnel Policies and Standards]).

Civil Status. Table 3 of the civil status of the respondents shows that out of the 100 percent of the employees, the status with highest percentage is married with 61.50 percent and 220 frequencies while the status with the lowest percentage amounting to 0.6 percent is widowed with the frequency of 2.

The majority of those working for national government agencies were found to be married. National government agencies are attractive places to work because they provide secure employment and a variety of desirable perks, including health insurance, paid leave, retirement programs, and security of tenure. These advantages may be especially tempting to married couples who are responsible for providing for their families.

The findings from Table 2, which indicate that the majority of NGA employees fall within the age brackets of 26 to 33 years old, align with the research conducted by the Asian Development Bank (2021). The study by the Asian Development Bank highlights that married couples in the Philippines are more inclined to be employed in government agencies compared to unmarried couples. Moreover, it suggests that married government employees tend to have longer tenures in their positions compared to unmarried government employees. Additionally, unmarried government employees are more likely to change occupations compared to their married counterparts.

This correlation between age distribution among NGA employees and marital status aligns with broader societal trends and preferences regarding employment and stability. Married individuals, often seeking stability for themselves and their families, may find the secure employment and benefits offered by government agencies particularly appealing. This preference for stability may result in longer tenures and less frequent job changes among married government employees compared to their unmarried counterparts.

The lowest result is categorized as widowed it implies that there are few widowed employees in NGAs. These implications encompass challenges faced by bereaved employees who may struggle to fulfill the requirements of their job, including extended work hours, frequent travel, and high levels of stress. This is particularly true for those who are also responsible for the care of children or other family members. Employees who have lost their spouse may choose to retire early for reasons such as health issues,

financial challenges, or a want to dedicate more time to their loved ones. Lastly, the death of a spouse may be a catastrophic ordeal, with significant consequences on an individual's physical and emotional well-being. Employees who have lost their spouse may have a higher likelihood of death. The result aligns with the findings of Elwert and Christakis (2008), which indicated that individuals who experience the loss of a spouse have a higher likelihood of mortality compared to those whose spouses are still alive. The study demonstrated a substantial 66 percent increase in the probability of mortality among individuals within the first 90 days following the death of their spouse. These findings held true for both males and females and suggested that the loss of a spouse could have significant implications for the mortality of both partners. This underscores the profound impact that the death of a spouse can have on an individual's health and well-being, highlighting the importance of social support and coping mechanisms during such difficult times.

Highest Educational Attainment. As shown in Table 4 about the respondents' educational attainment, out of the 358 respondents, the academical status with the highest frequency consist of 138 is under college graduate with 38.50 percent and the educational attainment with the lowest frequency falls under 3 different statuses all having 1 frequency with 0.30 percent namely: elementary graduate; high school graduate; and LLB (Bachelor of Laws).

The results showed that a large percentage of the people who took the survey have bachelor's degrees or a college graduate. One of the requirements for government positions are college degree or higher. This is because government jobs often involve complex tasks and responsibilities that require a high level of education and skills as many government jobs involve working with the public, managing complex projects, or developing and implementing policies and procedures.

The data from the Philippine Statistics Authority (2019) supports the observation that a majority (62 percent) of government employees in the Philippines possess at least a bachelor's degree. This finding is consistent with the results presented in Table 2, which indicate a significant number of respondents falling within the age range of 26 to 33 and holding at least a college degree. Government positions typically require a college degree or higher academic qualification, explaining the prevalence of individuals with at least a bachelor's degree in these roles.

The lower frequencies observed in the categories of elementary graduate and high school graduate suggest fewer opportunities for individuals without a bachelor's degree or higher. This aligns with data from the National Center for Education Statistics (2019), which indicates lower employment rates for individuals who have not completed high school or have only completed high school compared to those with a bachelor's degree or above.

Regarding the Bachelor of Laws (LL.B.) category, while it is less common among government employees, a portion of law school graduates do choose to pursue government employment. This is consistent with the findings of Rutz (2023), which

suggest that approximately 10 percent of law school graduates opt for government service. This indicates that while the typical career trajectory for law school graduates may involve working in private legal firms, a notable proportion still choose to enter government employment.

Monthly Income. In Table 5, it shows the data in connection with the profile of the respondents in terms of monthly income. Out of the 358 government employees, 164 of them falls under the income range of Php24,601.00 to 39,400.00 with 45.80 percent while the least of the respondents are under the range of Php115,001.00 to 211,200.00 with only one (1) respondent with 0.30 percent.

The finding revealed that most of the respondents have a salary range of ₱24,601.00 to ₱39,400.00. This signifies that government employees' salary structures are established in accordance with their years of service, educational attainment, and job title. The grade of compensation is in accordance with the level of accountability that is linked to the job. A significant proportion of government employees fall within the Salary Grade (SG) 11 to 17 category, denoting a monthly remuneration that spans from ₱24,601.00 to ₱39,400.00.

The data from the Philippine Statistics Authority (2023) highlights that a significant portion of government jobs are concentrated in the clerical and professional levels, which typically require a college degree or higher academic qualification. These positions often command salaries ranging from ₱24,601.00 to ₱39,400.00. Additionally, the median age of government employees is reported to be 38 years old, with a majority holding a college degree or higher. Individuals within this age range with a college degree are typically in the mid-career stage, possessing several years of experience, which can contribute to higher salaries.

Moreover, information from the Civil Service Commission (2023) indicates that a substantial 91 percent of career jobs in Region V are occupied at the 2nd level. These second-level positions encompass professional, technical, and scientific roles that entail non-supervisory or supervisory responsibilities. These roles typically require a minimum of four years of post-secondary education up to the Division Chief level, further emphasizing the prevalence of positions requiring higher education qualifications within the government sector.

With a lowest result is one having within the salary range of ₱115,001 to ₱211,200. This indicates that the salary range specified generally corresponds to roles associated with division heads/chiefs, department managers, or directors. Additionally, it discloses that most agencies have only an Officer in-charge (OIC), In-charge of office (ICO), or designated head, and not a full-fledged agency head. As per the criteria outlined in Civil Service Memorandum Circular 05-2016, the aforementioned positions require the following qualifications for appointment: a Master's degree or Certificate of Leadership and Management from the CSC; 4 to 5 years of experience in supervision or management; completion of a training program consisting of 40 to 120 hours of supervisory or management learning and development within the past five years;

certification as a career service professional; and a proficiency level ranging from intermediate to superior. Due to the specified criteria, several individuals are encountering challenges while attempting to apply for the positions.

Years in Service. Table 6 shows the data about the years in service of the respondents. It shows that the range with highest frequency consisting of 105 government employees is under 1 to 5 years with 29.20 percent while the range with lowest frequency with 3 government employees is under above 30 years with 0.80 percent.

The findings revealed that most of government employees in national government agencies in Daet, Camarines Norte are employed from one to five years and the lowest frequency is thirty (30) years and above. It would indicate that the organization has a high volume of employee turnover on a consistent basis. Because of this, employees may get the impression that their employer does not respect them or that they do not have the opportunity to grow and develop in their jobs. The contentment of the workforce may suffer because of this factor.

The observation that only a small percentage of government employees remain content with their organization and choose to stay and progress in their careers aligns with findings by Błoński and Jefmański (2013). Their research suggests a correlation between an employee's job satisfaction and the duration of their employment with the same company.

Job satisfaction encompasses various factors including management and supervision, compensation, communication, organizational culture, relationships with coworkers, and emotional exhaustion. Employees who have spent more years working for the same organization tend to report higher levels of job satisfaction.

Conversely, employees with fewer years of service may exhibit signs of dissatisfaction, which could be reflected in their shorter tenure with the organization. Their lower commitment to the organization may stem from various factors such as unmet expectations, dissatisfaction with the work environment, or a lack of opportunities for growth and development.

In summary, the length of an employee's tenure with an organization can serve as an indicator of their level of satisfaction and commitment to the company. Employees who choose to stay and advance within the organization over time are likely to be more content with their job and perceive greater opportunities for personal and professional development.

Level of Financial Literacy of the Respondents on Investment Decision

The researcher examined spending, saving, investing, and insurance. Ten relevant factors were utilized to quantify respondents' financial literacy to explain each variable. These statistics are in Tables 7 to 10.

Spending. The Table 7 shows that the overall weighted mean of the respondents under financial literacy in terms of spending is 3.65 which can be interpreted as agree. Out of the ten indicators under spending, all showed an interpretation of agree except on indicator stating “I purchased a financial product after gathering information about it. It has the lowest weighted mean amounting to 3.18 that can be interpreted as neither agree nor disagree. While the indicator with the highest weighted mean amounting to 3.91 and can be interpreted as agree states that “I keep my debt to a minimum to ensure timely payment”.

From the data collected and analyzed, it implies that the respondents can track their expenses, compare prices, and create and follow a budget. Furthermore, it serves as a positive indication of one's competence in financial literacy. It conveys the perception that they possess the ability to effectively handle their finances and are dedicated to fulfilling their financial obligations. Possessing this expertise is crucial for every investor as it reduces the probability of meeting financial problems in the future. It also suggests that they have knowledge about the potential dangers of debt and choose to avoid taking on debt until it is necessary. This enables individuals to have a greater amount of capital accessible for investments and reduces the probability of encountering financial hardships in the future.

Likewise, these are all important skills for making informed financial decisions. The respondents can distinguish between wants and needs, and they are able to resist the temptation to overspend. These are also important skills for making informed investment decisions (Lusardi, 2008; Campbell and Lusardi, 2009).

The respondents' ability to understand and adhere to the 70-20-10 rule reflects a positive financial mindset and a foundational understanding of budgeting principles. By allocating their income according to this rule, they demonstrate a commitment to managing their finances responsibly, prioritizing savings, and maintaining a balance between essential expenses and discretionary spending. This disciplined approach lays a solid groundwork for financial stability and long-term wealth accumulation.

Furthermore, the respondents' tendency to evaluate financial products before making a purchase signifies a thoughtful and informed approach to investment decisions. Their willingness to gather information and weigh the pros and cons of various investment options reflects a level of financial literacy that enables them to make prudent choices aligned with their financial goals and risk tolerance. This thorough analysis empowers them to select investments that suit their individual needs and preferences, ultimately contributing to their overall financial well-being.

Savings. Table 8 shows that the overall weighted mean under savings is 3.77 wherein it is interpreted as agree (A). All indicators showed an interpretation of agree (A) except for the indicator number seven (7) which indicates setting aside money for short and long-term financial goals with the lowest weighted mean of 3.27 with an interpretation of neither agree nor disagree (NAD). The indicator is all about setting aside money for the employees short-term and long-term financial goals. While the indicator with the highest

weighted mean amounting to 4.01 is indicator number (10) which states creating a budget for their financial obligation.

The respondents' agreement regarding the importance of budgeting for managing their financial affairs underscores their conscientious approach to financial management. By creating and adhering to a budget, they demonstrate a commitment to tracking their incomes and expenditures, setting achievable savings goals, and maintaining financial discipline. This organized approach to money management lays a solid foundation for making informed investment decisions and accumulating wealth over time.

Furthermore, their ability to stay well-informed about their financial situation suggests a high level of financial literacy. With a clear understanding of their incomes, expenses, and savings goals, they are better equipped to assess investment opportunities, weigh potential risks and rewards, and make decisions that align with their financial objectives. This proactive approach to financial planning and decision-making is essential for achieving long-term financial success and security.

It is supported by the findings of Stopler and Walter (2017), who made the assertion that individuals who have a complete comprehension of the significance of saving and who are actively working toward the accomplishment of their monetary goals are more likely to be successful in achieving those goals.

While the lowest with an indicator is setting aside money for short and long-term financial goals. It is an indication that they devise a strategy for how they will save and invest their money in the future. They are aware of how their money is being spent and can pinpoint areas in which they might reduce their spending to increase their savings. This may include a strategy of creating a savings account for unexpected expenses, a savings account for retirement, and a savings account for more immediate goals such as a down payment on a home or a new vehicle.

The conclusion drawn from your research aligns well with the findings of Gilenko and Chernova (2021), which emphasized the positive correlation between financial literacy and competent decision-making in investments and savings. Their study underscores that individuals with a higher level of financial literacy tend to make informed choices not only about investment strategies but also about savings plans, including those aimed at long-term objectives such as retirement.

This consistency between your research conclusions and the findings of Gilenko and Chernova highlights the importance of financial literacy in empowering individuals to navigate complex financial decisions effectively. It reinforces the notion that enhancing financial knowledge and skills can lead to better financial outcomes and increased preparedness for future financial goals and challenges.

Investing. Table 9 shows information which details the level of financial literacy of the respondents with reference to the decision-making process under investing. The overall weighted mean is 3.62, which may be interpreted as agree. There was a total of

10 indicators that were applied in order to ascertain the level of financial literacy that the staff members possessed in relation to the subject of investing. Except for indicators number 2 and 4, which stated, respectively, "I invest in real estate, shares, stocks, bonds, or investment opportunities," and "my current investment portfolio is diversified to balance the risks," their weighted mean was the lowest at 3.32, and their interpretation was neither agree nor disagree which means that the respondents neither agree nor disagree on the stated indicator. There was a consensus among all of the other indications that indicated agreement. Despite the fact that the indicator number one, which has the highest weighted mean of 3.90, asserts that "I am well aware about my risk tolerance," the other indicators do not make this claim. According to this interpretation (A), the word "agree" can be understood.

The data that were gathered and analyzed indicate that in terms of investment decision along investing the respondents are aware of their comfort level with taking risks and that they are also able to comprehend the fundamentals of the various investment products. Since they are aware of the level of risk they are willing to take, they will be in a better position to select investments that are suitable for their requirements and objectives. This is because they understand the potential benefits and dangers associated with various kinds of investments, allowing them to select investments that are suitable for own level of comfort with risk.

McBride (2023) found that knowing how much risk you're okay with is really important when you're trying to make more money without stressing out all the time. Understanding your risk tolerance helps you make a plan for investing that deals with ups and downs in the economy while also giving you a chance to make more money.

The lowest result is associated with two indicators: investing in real estate, shares, stocks, bonds or investment opportunities and own current investment portfolio is diversified to balance the risks. This suggests that the participants are making sensible investment choices and taking steps to grow their wealth gradually, ultimately achieving their financial goals effectively. In addition, they engage in diversification as a means of limiting the potential consequences of risk or financial loss. Prior to making any investments, it is essential to possess a comprehensive understanding of the potential hazards, since there is always the potential for experiencing financial losses.

Bernadene's study in 2019 backs the notion that being good with money is linked to making smarter investment choices. The research showed that people who understand finances better tend to invest more in things like stocks and bonds, and they usually end up making more money from their investments.

Availing Insurance. Table 10 shows that the overall weighted mean under availing insurance is 3.63 which is interpreted as agree. The indicator with the highest weighted mean is indicator number 10 which states "I understand that insurance companies earn money by investing the premiums I pay" with a score of 3.77 and is interpreted as agree. It is all about the understanding of the employees on how the insurance companies earn money. While the lowest weighted mean is indicator number

2. It states “I am familiar with the procedures involved in insurance” with a score of 3.51 and can be interpreted as agree. It shows being familiar with the procedures involved in insurance that can be interpreted as agree and it is all about the procedures involved in insurance companies.

The table reveals that in terms of investment decision along availing the indicator understanding that insurance companies earn money by investing the premiums the customer pays. This suggest that there is a positive relationship between financial literacy and insurance literacy. Individuals with a solid grasp of these concepts are better equipped to assess the investment performance of their insurance business and make informed decisions regarding their insurance coverage. It implies that they knew that their insurance premiums help these companies to sustain their businesses while in turn, helping the customers secure their investments.

Proof of this comes from research by Gilenko and Chernova (2021) that shows people who are financially literate are more likely to save for long-term goals like retirement. People who are financially literate are more likely to get insurance policies that suit their needs.

The lowest result in terms of investment decision along availing is the indicator: I am familiar with the procedures involved in insurance. It suggests that they have a greater degree of financial literacy and can comprehend the significance of insurance as well as the many kinds of insurance that are available and how to select the appropriate insurance for their requirements.

Bernadene (2019) found evidence supporting a positive link between financial literacy and having insurance. The research suggests that individuals with better financial knowledge tend to select the appropriate insurance coverage for their requirements, avoiding both over-insurance and underinsurance.

The study also found that there is a relationship between financial literacy and insurance knowledge. People with higher levels of financial literacy are more likely to be aware of the different types of insurance available to them and are more likely to understand the terms and conditions of insurance policies.

Test for Significant Relationship between the Profile of the Respondents and their Level of Financial Literacy on Investment Decision

The test for significant relationships that may exist between the profile of the respondents and the level of financial literacy on investment decisions were determined by applying the Contingency Coefficient (C) and the Somers' Delta Correlation Coefficient (d).

Table 11 shows that the financial literacy on investment decisions along spending has no significant relationship along the profile of the respondents (sex, age, civil status,

educational attainment, years in service) except for monthly income ($d=0.129$, $p\text{-value}=.004$).

It means that financial literacy on spending has nothing to do with age, sex, educational attainment, civil status and years in service. However, their monthly income ($p\text{-value}<.05$) is affected by their level of financial literacy on spending. It implies that age, sex, educational attainment, civil status and years in service are not determinants in the level of financial literacy of the respondents along spending or their financial literacy on spending is not determined by their profile. Their diverse background may not exhibit similar levels of financial literacy in this specific aspect. On the other hand, an individual's monthly income is somewhat influenced by their level of financial literacy in spending. It means that there are people who are more financial literate in managing their expenditures and may have a better grasp of how to optimize their income. Also, according to Manoj (2021) more knowledgeable employees cut down expenses while they are in money problems and maintain detailed records.

In addition, the level of financial literacy on investment decisions in terms of savings has no significant relationship along age, civil status, educational attainment, and years in service. Those profiles are not considered determinants in the level of financial literacy on decision making along with savings. However, the same variable has significant relationship along sex ($C=-.178$, $p\text{-value}=.020$) and monthly income ($d=-.180$, $p\text{-value}=.000$), meaning both $p\text{-values}$ are less than $.05$ ($p\text{-values}<.05$). The results imply that on the average, females have lower level of financial literacy in terms of savings compared to males. According to Mamush's study (2022), there was a noticeable difference in financial literacy between men and women, with more men falling into the higher category and more women in the lower category. Additionally, Gerzon and Lopena (2023) suggest that women may have lower financial literacy due to self-esteem issues. Furthermore, the research indicates that as respondents' income increases, their level of financial literacy regarding investment decisions and savings tends to decrease. Therefore, both gender and monthly income can be considered factors influencing financial literacy in investment decisions and savings.

Further, the level of financial literacy on investment decision along investing has no significant relationship in the profile in terms of age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, and years in service but not in the monthly income ($d= .199$, $p\text{-value}=.010$) since the $p\text{-value}$ is less than $.05$ ($p\text{-value}<.05$). It means that age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, and number of years in business are not predictors when it comes to the level of financial literacy on investment decisions. On the other hand, the monthly income is a significant factor related to the level of financial literacy in the context of investment decisions. The positive coefficient value (0.199) suggests that, on average, individuals with higher income tend to have a higher level of financial literacy regarding investments. This implies that the respondents with greater financial resources may have a better understanding of investment options strategies.

Murmu's study (2023) also suggests that individuals with lower income or resources tend to have lower levels of financial literacy, while those with higher income

tend to have higher levels of financial literacy. Similarly, Manoj's research (2021) indicates that more knowledgeable employees place greater importance on investing in shares and other investment opportunities.

Finally, the financial literacy on investment decisions along availing has no significant relationship along the profile on age, civil status, educational attainment, monthly income, and years in service except for the sex profile of the respondents. The sex profile ($C = .228$, $p\text{-value} = .001$) has significant relationship in the level of financial literacy on investment decisions along availing. The sex of the respondents, whether male or female is significantly related to the financial literacy along the variable considered. In other words, men and women in the sample may have different levels of financial literacy in this context. This could have important implications for financial education and investment strategies targeted toward specific sex groups.

Nevertheless, other characteristics, such as age, civil status, educational attainment, monthly income, and years of service, are examples of demographic indicators that do not accurately indicate an individual's capacity to make educated judgments regarding investments. In general, there is no substantial association between the profile of the respondents and the amount of financial literacy on investment decisions, including spending, saving, investing, and availing. Similar findings were found in the research conducted by Gerzon and Lopena (2023), which found that the demographics of their respondents were unable to provide a definitive association regarding their respondents' level of financial literacy.

Problems Affecting the Financial Literacy on Investment Decision of the Respondents

Table 12 shows the ten (10) problems affecting the financial Literacy of National Government employees. It exhibits that the main problem the respondents are facing is Budget constraints and resource allocation with a frequency of 189. While the least problem is Technological advancements with a frequency of 38.

Financial literacy is the ability to understand and use financial information to make informed decisions about money. It is an essential skill for everyone, regardless of their age, income, or background. However, many people lack the necessary financial knowledge and skills to make sound investment decisions. There are several problems that affects financial literacy on investment decisions. These include budget constraints and resource allocation, heavy workload, limited financial training opportunities, limited time, lack of financial incentives, lack of awareness of investment options, complex insurance policies, limited access to independent financial advice, risk-averse culture, and technological advancements. A person's capacity to make prudent investing decisions might be severely impaired by these issues. The likelihood of people losing a lot of money due to scams, investing in things that aren't a good fit, or making dangerous investments increases when people don't know how to handle their money.

The highest rank out of all the stated problems affecting the financial literacy on investment decision is budget constraints and resource allocation. It means that a significant number of individuals do not have the financial resources to invest, as well as the time and resources necessary to learn about investing. People who are struggling to meet their financial obligations and find it difficult to properly allocate their resources may have a tough time investing in their own financial future. There is a possibility that they might not have sufficient funds to put money down for a down payment on a property or to invest in stocks or bonds. It is also possible that they do not have the time or resources necessary to learn about investing or to handle the investments they do have.

The study conducted by the Financial Industry Regulatory Authority (2018) provides evidence supporting the notion that low-income households face challenges accessing financial education resources. Additionally, the study suggests that households with lower incomes tend to make less prudent financial decisions compared to those with higher incomes.

While the least challenge affecting the financial literacy on decision making of the respondents is technological advancement. It implies that most people believe that technology is helping them to make more informed investment decisions. Technology has made it easier for people to access financial information and to invest in a variety of assets such as people can use online brokerages to invest in stocks, bonds, and ETFs. They can also use robo-advisors to create and manage investment portfolios. It is very easy right now to avail investments using online platforms and means such as e-mails, online meeting platforms as meetups, submitting documents via online and processing payments using online payment platforms: GCash, Paymaya and online banking applications.

Majbour (2023) corroborates this finding by highlighting that technology has made investing more accessible and affordable for people across different income levels. In the past, investing was primarily accessible to the wealthy, who could afford expensive investment products and professional financial advice. However, with the advent of technology, individuals can now invest in various assets like stocks, bonds, and ETFs, as long as they have internet access. Additionally, there are numerous free investing platforms available, which streamline the process of starting to invest.

The challenges impacting financial literacy in investment decisions are considerable and can greatly affect individuals' financial stability. Research indicates that individuals with limited financial knowledge are prone to making risky investments, choosing unsuitable products, or becoming victims of scams, resulting in substantial financial losses. To address these issues and empower individuals to make informed financial decisions, it is crucial to enhance access to financial education, streamline financial products and services, combat misinformation and scams, and assist individuals in recognizing and overcoming behavioral biases.

Formulated IEC Materials to Improve the Financial Literacy of the Respondents on Investment Decision

The Information, Education, and Communication (IEC) Materials were created using the research study's findings. It would help to enhance the degree of financial literacy among national government employees.

The content comprises visual representations of data about financial literacy and its significance, budget creation, the rationale behind saving, initiation of investments and understanding one's risk tolerance, financial planning, various investment products, and sample financial trackers.

The aforementioned topics were selected to address the respondents' limited understanding of various investment opportunities, the need for portfolio diversification, the significance of conducting thorough research prior to purchasing financial products, the allocation of funds for both short-term and long-term financial objectives, the reduction of savings, budgetary limitations, and the low level of financial literacy among women.

The provided IEC materials will assist individuals in enhancing their existing level of financial literacy, addressing any deficiencies in their financial literacy, and enhancing their financial understanding. Succeeding pages show the crafted IEC materials for national government employees and other users.

This addresses the importance of financial literacy, understanding fundamental finance concepts to prevent scams, mastering saving and budgeting techniques to effectively allocate funds for short and long-term financial objectives, determining risk profile to assess risk tolerance, and selecting suitable investments from various options in the market.

Findings

The study's notable findings, as determined from the collected data, are as follows:

1. In connection with the profile of the respondents, the results of the survey on the 358 respondents of national government employees are as follows: in terms of sex profile 39.7 percent male and 60.3 percent female. In terms of age range: 18 to 25 is 2.2 percent; 26 to 33 is 28.5 percent; 34 to 41 is 22.3 percent; 42 to 49 is 24.3 percent; 50 to 57 is 14.5 percent; and 58 to 65 is 8.1 percent. In terms of civil status: 31 percent are single; 61.5 percent are married; 1.4 percent are separated; and 0.6 percent are widowed.

Under respondents' educational attainment: elementary graduate, high school graduate and LLB are all 0.3 percent; high school level with 0.8 percent; college level with 2.5 percent; college graduate with 38.5 percent; with units in masters is 33.8 percent; master's degree holder with 12.3 percent; with units in doctorate is 4.7 percent; and doctorate degree holder is 6.4 percent. In terms of

monthly income: below 13,000.00 is 1.7 percent; 13,001.00 to 17,500.00 is 8.9 percent; 17,501.00 to 24,600.00 is 18.7 percent; 24,601.00 to 39,400.00 is 45.8 percent; 39,401.00 to 63,500.00 is 15.6 percent; 63,501.00 to 115,000.00 is 8.9 percent; and 115,001.00 to 211,200.00 is 0.3 percent. In terms of years in service: 1 to 5 is 29.2 percent; 6 to 10 is 24.9 percent; 11 to 15 is 15.9% percent; 16 to 20 is 9.2 percent; 21 to 25 is 8.1 percent; 26 to 30 is 5.9 percent; and above 30 is 0.8 percent.

2. The national government employees' level of financial literacy on investment decision along spending shows an overall weighted mean of 3.65 which is interpreted as agree. All ten (10) indicators showed an interpretation of agree except in purchasing a financial product after gathering information. It has a weighted mean of 3.18 with an interpretation of neither agree nor disagree (NAD). In terms of financial literacy along savings, it resulted to an overall weighted mean of 3.77 with an interpretation of agree. All ten (10) indicators showed an interpretation of agree except on the indicator about setting aside money for short and long-term financial goals. It has a weighted mean of 3.27 with an interpretation of neither agree nor disagree.

While under investing, it showed an overall weighted mean of 3.62 with an interpretation of agree on all ten (10) indicators under investing resulted in an interpretation of agree except for the two (2) indicators about investing into investment opportunities and doing diversification to balance the risks. Both has a weighted mean of 3.32 and an interpretation of nether agree nor disagree. Lastly, the level of financial literacy in terms of availing insurance shows an overall weighted mean of 3.63 with an interpretation of agree.

3. There is no significant relationship between age, sex, educational achievement, civil position, and years in service with the amount of financial knowledge on spending. Nevertheless, the amount of financial literacy has a significant impact on monthly income ($p\text{-value} < .05$) with regards to spending habits. An individual's monthly income is partially determined by their level of financial literacy regarding expenditure. Individuals with a higher level of financial literacy in controlling their expenses are likely to possess a greater understanding of how to maximize their revenue.

There is no significant relationship between the amount of financial literacy regarding investment decisions in terms of savings and factors such as age, civil status, educational attainment, and years in service. Nevertheless, there is a strong correlation between sex ($C = -0.178$, $p\text{-value} = 0.020$) and monthly income ($d = -0.180$, $p\text{-value} = 0.000$) with the level of financial literacy in connection to investment decision-making in the context of saves. The findings suggest that, on average, females may possess a lesser degree of financial literacy in relation to saves as compared to males. Similarly, it emphasizes the importance of financial literacy in relation to monthly income and savings. The negative number suggests that when respondents' income improves, there is a tendency for their degree of

financial literacy regarding investment decisions and savings to drop. Therefore, both gender and monthly income can be regarded as factors that influence the level of financial literacy while making investment decisions and saving.

There is no significant association between the level of financial literacy on investment decision and the profile characteristics of age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, and years in service. However, there is a significant relationship with monthly income ($d = 0.199$, $p\text{-value} = 0.010$). It plays a crucial role in determining the level of financial literacy while making investment decisions. The positive coefficient value (0.199) indicates that persons with higher income often possess a higher level of financial literacy in relation to investments. This suggests that individuals who have more financial resources may possess a more comprehensive comprehension of investment methods and possibilities.

There is no significant association between financial literacy about investment decisions and insurance availability, and the demographic factors of age, civil status, educational attainment, monthly income, and years in service, save for the respondents' sex profile. The sex profile, with a correlation coefficient of 0.228 and a $p\text{-value}$ of 0.001, exhibits a strong association with the level of financial literacy in connection to investment decision-making and insurance utilization. The respondents' sex, whether male or female, is strongly associated with financial literacy across the investigated variables. Put simply, the individuals of both genders in the sample may possess varying degrees of financial literacy within this setting. This could have significant ramifications for financial education and investing strategies aimed at various gender groups.

4. The study gathered ten (10) existing problems that affects the respondent's financial literacy on investment decisions. The problems encountered are the following: budget constraints and resource allocation as ranked 1st with 189 frequencies; heavy workload ranked 2nd with 170 frequency; limited financial training opportunities ranked 3rd with 156 frequency; while risk-averse culture ranked 9th with 59 frequency; and technological advancements ranked 10th with 38 frequency.
5. Based on the findings of the study, the intervention to improve the financial literacy of the respondents is to develop an Information, Education, and Communication (IEC) materials which contain or outline what financial literacy is and why is it essential. It will also include fundamental financial ideas and principles, financial planning, and budgeting, saving, investing, and that will aid the gap on the current financial literacy of the respondents in terms of spending, saving, investing, and availing insurance. Participants will also get access to financial trackers to help them manage their money. These trackers can assist individuals in keeping track of their expenditures, saving for objectives, and budgeting successfully.

Conclusions

The researcher drew the following conclusions based on the findings of the study:

1. Many of the respondents are female, ages 26 to 33, married, college graduate or with college degree, has a month income of Php 24,601.00 to Php 39,400.00, and 1 to 5 years in service.
2. The level of financial literacy on investment decision along spending, saving, investing, and availing insurance all have an interpretation of agree.
3. The level of financial literacy on investment decisions along spending, savings, investing, and availing insurance has no significant relationship on age, marital status, educational attainment, and length of service. However, monthly income has a significant relationship with spending, savings, and investing while sex has a significant relationship with savings and availing insurance.
4. The main problem that the national government employees in Daet, Camarines Norte encounters is budget constraints and resource allocation.
5. 5. Based on the findings of the study, the IEC Materials were developed to improve the level of financial literacy of the respondents. Also to further improve the financial literacy of national government employees, an intervention plan for institutionalizing IEC material has been developed.

Recommendations

The researcher has formulated conclusions and recommendations based on the findings:

1. The national government agencies may provide financial literacy activities to their employees, regardless of age, sex, education, or income. Budgeting, saving, investing, and insurance will be covered in the course. It may also address government employees' benefits and retirement planning demands. They may also require financial literacy training for new government hires. Before starting work, all workers will have a basic awareness of financial ideas and principles.
2. The training program that the national government agencies along with the Bureau of the Treasury will provide may focused on introducing different investment opportunities like shares, stocks, bond, index funds and many more. They may also highlight on how to diversify different financial products. Als a thorough discussion may be included for the respondents to know how to gather significant data about the products/services they are going to avail to avoid risks. Strategies on how to effectively allocate funds will also be included. The facilitators may also invite financial advisors, experts from financial institutions, and representatives from insurance companies.
3. The national government agencies may disseminate the IEC materials along with the financial tracker to aid the government employees specially the females to track their expenses that may help in increasing their savings. They may see in the trackers if they have bad spending habits or some aspects to improve. It can also

be modified to indicate the records of existing investments of the workers so they can also track down their investment and its interest earnings. Additionally, future researcher may to consider other profiles not included in the study, to know if other profiles have significant relationships with the existing factors.

4. The national government agencies may introduce to their employees the different investing opportunities available in the market that eve low-income earners may avail. Interest earnings from the investment will become an additional source of income for them. The employees may still utilize the financial trackers for them to see where they can still lessen their spending to add for their available funds.
5. The proposed intervention plan and the IEC materials may be used by the different national government agencies to improve the level of financial literacy of their employees. Government employees may also continuously monitor their income and expenses to know their financial standing. Future researcher may enhance the given IEC in accordance with the changing needs of the government employees. Future researcher may suggest new or enhance financial tracker for monitoring of the investment and insurance of the government employees

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Prior to the initiation of the study, the researcher secured explicit informed consent from all participants. Formal request letters were submitted to the relevant government agencies, outlining the study's objectives and the researchers' commitment to ethical conduct. The letters emphasized the protection of participant rights, including data privacy and confidentiality. The researcher committed to conducting the study independently and free from any personal or financial interests that could influence the findings and to maintain strict adherence to academic integrity, ensuring that there was no plagiarism in the study. Upon careful review, the agencies granted their approval, facilitating the researchers' access to the target population. This approval was a crucial step in ensuring the study's legitimacy and ethical compliance.

Acknowledgments

The researcher would like to express his gratitude and thankfulness to the Almighty God for the many benefits that He has bestowed upon him during this study endeavor.

He also expresses his profound appreciation to those individuals who, in some way or another, contributed to the completion of this study by providing moral, mental, and financial support. Without their assistance, the researcher would not have been able to finish this work.

Giving thanks, gratitude and appreciation to his adviser, Dr. Gehana D. Lamug, DBA; for providing him with essential advice during the whole process of this study. She instructed him on the approaches that should be used to carry out the study and to present the findings and details of the research in the most understandable manner. Her strength, vision, genuineness, and motivation have been a significant source of inspiration for him.

Having the opportunity to learn under her guidance was both an honor and a wonderful experience.

He would like to express gratitude to the members of the panel of the thesis committee; Rusty G. Abanto, PhD, Professor V, Jennifer S. Rubio, PhD, Associate Professor V and Jefferson T. Dacer, CPA, MBA, Chief Administrative Officer for their support, advice, and insightful remarks.

To Jennifer S. Rubio, PhD, his statistician, for her invaluable expertise in the statistical treatment of data of his manuscript.

The heads of offices of national government agencies who willingly complied with the requested data and permitted him to perform his research study to their respective offices and agencies.

Those government employees of their respective national government agencies which served as the respondents, the researchers utmost appreciation. Without their willingness to share their precious time and providing honest responses, this research study will not be possible.

To all the people within the Bureau of the Treasury Camarines Norte Provincial Office who gave their valuable insights and made the office my breathing ground during my thesis study.

In addition, the researcher would like to express his gratitude to his close friends, colleagues, and loved ones for their love, support, encouragement, and inspiration. Their love and support were endless, and they are the strength that keep him at his toes even in complicated and difficult situations. They are his reinforcement in his tough moments and the driving force to keep him on waking, looking forward for another day.

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